

Bus Route Classification for Rural Areas using Graph Convolutional Networks

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Abstract. In this paper, we present a new approach to determine the estimated time of arrival (ETA) for bus routes using (Deep) Graph Convolutional Networks (DGCNs). In addition, we use the same DGCN to detect detours within a route. In our application, a classification of routes and their underlying graph structure is performed using Graph Learning. Our model leads to a fast prediction and avoids solving the vehicle routing problem (VRP) through expensive computations. Moreover, we describe how to predict travel time for all routes using the same DGCN Model. This method makes it possible not to use a more computationally intensive approximation algorithm when determining long travel times with many intermediate stops, but to use our network for an early estimate of the quality of a route. Long travel times, in our case result from the use of a call-bus system, which must distribute many passengers among several vehicles and can take them to places without a regular stop. For a case study, the rural town of Roding in Bavaria is used. Our training data for this area results from an approximation algorithm that we implemented to optimize routes and generate an archive of routes of varying quality simultaneously.

Keywords: VRP · Graph Learning · Graph Convolutional Networks

1 Introduction

Public transport is playing a more important role than ever before. Modern technologies, like mobile applications, offer many opportunities to make it as accessible and sustainable as possible for both travelers and service providers. With an ever-increasing number of ways to collect, store, process and disseminate large amounts of data, the role of public transport is becoming even more important. Those growing number of options can create benefits for many areas of local public transport and mobility in general.

Especially in rural areas, bus connections are often sparse, although it is precisely there that the distances to be covered, for example, to go shopping, are very long. Therefore, this area in particular can benefit greatly from efficient

local public transport solutions. This paper deals specifically with improving routes, which are used in a call-bus system with ride-sharing options for rural areas.

The authors of this work cooperate with the bus operators in Roding and help them with the establishment of a new minibus service, where so-called feeders, are being tested for public transport in the Roding area. In the future, public transport in Roding will not operate via fixed routes and stops anymore, but those feeders will pick up passengers at dynamically generated stops near their homes and bring them to their desired destinations. These stops are created using a geometric algorithm that weighs positions according to the number of POIs nearby and population [2]. Especially for rural areas, such dynamic stops and timetables have advantages, as residents have shorter distances to cover and are more flexible in terms of time, for example when they have to attend appointments. The presented research is a step towards improving mobility in rural areas and developing a mobility-on-demand solution for rural areas within the scope of the Bavarian High-Tech and Smart City Initiative [25].

To solve the VRP, an algorithm was developed to find the fastest route for multiple vehicles simultaneously. In this iterative process, the authors came up with the idea of using the individual quality levels of the routes to develop an ETA prediction. For this purpose, graph learning methods are used. The idea is not to replace the exact algorithm with a machine learning model but to give a much faster estimate of the ETA, which does not have to be absolutely reliable. Especially since there are many vehicles in public transport that need to be calculated at the same time, it makes sense to use graph learning to get a quick first estimation.

The use of this system is therefore necessary on the one hand to achieve a speedup in the determination of optimal routes. On the other hand, it can also be beneficial for the individual user. It is often the case that bus drivers take a diversion even though there would be a shorter route. Our system could point out such shortcuts and alternative routes. Moreover, nowadays it is inevitable to deal with real-time data when solving the VRP. Thus, there must be a combination of an information system with the route planning algorithm [21].

As a further step, our neural network model should also estimate the estimated time of arrival (ETA). Since this is a regression, the result must be much more accurate than in our initial use case of classification, which means that a much larger data set must be used. For the implementation of this prediction, a modified model in the form of a Deep Graph Convolutional Network (DGCN) was trained.

These DGCNs can be optimally suited for application to public transport problems. Roads and routes can be represented as graphs with weights assigned to each edge, making it easy to abstract and evaluate a route.

In rural areas, there are far fewer regular bus connections, so a possibility must be created to transport people regardless of time restrictions. Here, too, the use of a GCN is optimal, since it can also store the time characteristics of the

rigid bus routes and thus corresponding weak points in the complete timetable can be detected more quickly.

Once a network has been trained, it can be scaled to a larger region or transferred to another region with a similar problem and structure, i.e. the number of parameters is independent of the number of nodes in a network. Our model is therefore not only applicable to the city of our case study but can also be applied to other cities without further adaptation.

Fig. 1. Map with a diversion around point 6 to be recognized by our GCN.

Figure 1 shows a subroute on the basis of which our graph is created. Pay particular attention to point no. 6, which leads to an extension of the route and is recognized as a necessary diversion because the route from point no. 5 back to the start is via a different route.

In Section 2, we will first discuss related work for the classification of routes. Moreover, we show that inference via graph learning is faster than traditional approximation algorithms. This is followed by a description of the general problem to be solved by graph learning in Section 3. In Section 4 we describe the methods used for our model. In Section 5 we give a presentation and evaluation of the results of our (D)GCNs. Section 6 rounds off this paper with an outlook on further improvements that we plan to implement.

2 Related Work

Over the last decades, the VRP has become ever more important [11,24,18]. In parallel the tools have been continuously improved, making it by now possible to plan an optimal route for multiple vehicles in little time.

An early approach was to provide the individual sub-routes in a hierarchical structure based on selection criteria [14]. Here, emphasis is placed on the ranking and sorting of alternatives. The two most widespread selection criteria are still "shortest path" and "least time". For the human navigator, however, a mix of these two route selection criteria is usually an optimal route. For example, a certain route is longer but offers more comfort for the passengers.

In recent years, sensors and devices for wireless communication have also become increasingly affordable, allowing modern route planning to take place in real-time [27]. When classifying systems for route planning, a distinction can be made between systems with different design approaches. For example, there are reactive and predictive systems or static and dynamic systems [27]. With the introduction of our GCN, we want to create a static predictive system, one that can react to changes in the planning of an optimal route at any time through new training using live data.

In order to improve graph learning with knowledge from other areas, some techniques were adopted. Driven by various successful applications in computer vision, recently the interest has emerged to also generalize convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to the non-Euclidean geometry of graphs [4].

Many real-world applications work with data that can be represented in the form of graphs: e.g. social networks, biological or chemical structures, and transport networks [26]. Graph learning refers to a part of machine learning that works with graphs [28]. Due to the diverse and abundant occurrence of data that can be represented as graphs and the possibility of using them to gain new insights, graph learning has gained popularity [16]. GNNs are also used to predict brain activity, help predict disease, or are used to solve a number of optimization problems in wireless networks [30,23,22].

The goal of graph learning is to extract the desired features from a graph. Here, the tasks can be divided into three different layers that can be used. A classification/regression of single attributes of nodes, edges between nodes, or of the complete graph can be performed [6]. In our case of route classification, we are particularly concerned with the classification of a complete graph and the similarity of a graph to other graphs.

Due to the already described versatile occurrence of data in the form of graphs or networks, a number of proposals have been made in recent years for extending neural network models to deal optimally with graphs. Such models exist both based on Recurrent Neural Networks and on Convolutional Neural Networks.

A concept that is similar to Graph Neural Networks is given by Message Passing Neural Networks, as introduced by Gilmer et al. in 2017 [12]. These are also models that propagate information between nodes in a graph. However, we use graphs specifically for representing routes.

Since the data of a Geo Information System (GIS) is also structured as a graph, the idea of using Graph Neural Networks as a tool to solve a VRP as efficiently as possible is obvious. In their survey paper, Jiang et al. compile papers dealing with vehicle speed prediction, traffic prediction, and passenger flow pre-

diction [17]. They also list a variety of different Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), such as GCNs or graph attention networks, which are used to solve traffic forecasting problems. However, the problem of estimating routes or determining ETA has not yet been analyzed by these authors.

A new approach to predicting ETA using GNNs is to use Google Maps data for the analysis. Complex spatiotemporal interactions (such as the start of rush hour) can be predicted [10]. Thus, it can be seen that the optimal planning and classification of routes is an ideal goal for the use of a GCN due to a large number of usable parameters. In our case, all training data are generated by the different phases of our HGS algorithm and there is no need to use artificially corrupted data like in other work.

Our discovery that during the iterations of an approximation algorithm, which continually improves a result valuable training data can be extracted, wherefrom a ML model can be built for rating the quality of unknown sample data is another contribution of this work, which has also applications outside the public transport area.

3 Formulation of the Problem

All routes and stops discussed in this paper are located in the vicinity of the small town of Roding, Bavaria. The town of Roding has about 11500 inhabitants (as of 2008) in an area of $113km^2$. In addition to the town of Roding itself, the complete neighboring region with an area of $674km^2$ is considered. A total of 2000 virtual stops were defined, using our software, within this area to cover it optimally and to have enough points to generate a long desirable route.

We use a hybrid genetic search (HGS) algorithm to solve the resulting special form of the vehicle routing problem for multiple vehicles and passengers simultaneously [3]. This algorithm must be run anew for the calculation of each route or each problem and requires a certain amount of time until the termination criterion is reached. The termination criterion here is either a fixed maximum of iterations or the absence of any improvements after a number of iterations. Routes determined by a Hybrid Genetic Search (HGS) algorithm are used as training data for the graph learning models. This algorithm is used to solve the capacitated vehicle routing problem with pickups and deliveries (CVRPPD) [29].

We use the data that the algorithm uses during route optimization to train the model of a graph learning network. Our model should predict the ETA for each passenger and additionally determine whether the chosen route is good or bad. The approach to use a GCN is intended to cover two areas of application: On the one hand, the algorithm already in use is accelerated by providing the neural network with intermediate results as input and terminating the calculations if it already assumes an optimal route. This leads to an improvement in runtime of up to 90%. On the other hand, the GCN must also function independently and inform the user whether a route he wants to take is optimal or whether it makes sense to choose an alternative route. An example of this would be the choice between a motorway with a higher driving speed and a longer driving distance

instead of a country road. This is especially important when used with our call-bus system, where multiple routes are calculated simultaneously and significant time savings can be achieved by identifying non-optimal routes faster.

This algorithm minimizes the cost of a route for a given number of pickup points from which goods, in this case, travelers, are picked up and their destinations (delivery points). This includes minimizing the number of vehicles actually needed and the route length. The results of this algorithm are optimized bus routes with actual and virtual stops in and around the Roding area. An optimal route is defined as the route that takes the least time, so we optimize for the shortest time instead of the shortest distance.

To enable their use as input parameters for the GCN, these routes must be converted into a graph representation. The distances between the respective points correspond to the edges. The graphs are homogeneous, which means they have only one node type and one edge type.

Based on the work of Bruna et al. [5] and Defferdard et al. [9], Kipf and Welling [20] have proposed a simple and efficient first-order approximation of the localized spectral graph-filtering. The layer-wise activity in such a multi-layer graph convolutional network (GCN) is thereby obtained by:

$$H^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(\tilde{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{A} \tilde{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} H^{(l)} W^{(l)} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $H^{(l)}$ denotes the activation of the previous layer l and $\tilde{A} = A + I_N$ represents the adjacency matrix of a graph \mathcal{G} with added self-connections. Further I_N is the identity matrix, and $\tilde{D}_{ii} = \sum_j \tilde{A}_{ij}$ denotes the degree matrix. The activation function is given by $\sigma(\cdot)$ and $W^{(l)}$ represents a matrix of trainable weights, and for our application we used the ReLU activation function $\text{ReLU}(\cdot) = \max(0, \cdot)$. In the first layer the input is given by $H^{(0)} = X$ and the final predictions in layer L are generated using a dense layer with one output neuron. In our proposed application of GCNs, the input features $X \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F}$ are given by the altitude, location and also distance, and travel time as edge weights between every single node. These features were selected because latitude and longitude describe the stops most accurately and are available for each stop. This also applies to altitude - this was furthermore added as a feature because, for example, fuel consumption, and the willingness of residents and tourists to ascend a significant height to reach a bus stop play a role in the quality of the routes. The distance between two points as an edge feature was added because it best describes the route segments additionally to the required journey time. Other parameters have been omitted so far to keep the model as simple as possible.

The complete network with all layers used is shown in Figure 2. During learning the weights $W^{(l)}$ are trained using the Adam optimizer [19]. A good trade-off between computational complexity and model accuracy was found using two GCN layers connected in series. They are used for each node to process the local structure information and to collect feature information. In the *mean pooling layer*, the node representations are combined to create a graph representation. This graph representation is then used as input for two successive *fully connected layers*. The fully connected layers are classic feedforward networks in which the

Fig. 2. Structure of the Graph Convolutional Network used

input representations are combined and the prediction result is calculated using the activation function. In the output layer, the sigmoid activation function is used to perform the classification, which is suitable for binary classifications [7]. Binary Cross Entropy is used as a suitable loss function [15].

4 Methods (Implementation)

We used the StellarGraph Machine Learning Library to implement the GCN. This is a library for graph machine learning that is built on the basis of TensorFlow and the Keras high-level API [8]. This library is based on the widely used Tensorflow platform and is therefore easy to use.

4.1 Data collection and Import

Since our training data is generated by an approximation algorithm, we know that arbitrary data that is produced within the first iterations of the procedure is non-optimal and can therefore be labeled as non-optimal solutions for our data set. The calculated solutions from the algorithm are considered optimal solutions, i.e. routes with the lowest travel time. In order to incorporate further geo-information, in the form of elevation data, into the training data of the model we also queried the Google Maps Platform Services [13].

In more detail, the *Directions Advanced API* was used to obtain complete routes with more than 10 stops. The *Directions API* was used to obtain edge features, travel times, and distances between two points on those routes. In total, nearly 1500 queries were made to the Directions Advanced API, and 220,000 queries were made to the Directions API to train our networks.

For each node of the graph, the fields *longitude*, *latitude*, *height* and for each edge the fields *distance* and *travel time* are imported. The request just described was made for all existing and virtual stops. These stops are contained in two CSV files, the virtual stops contain only latitude and longitude, the existing stops also contain information such as the address. These two files represent the pool from which the stops for the route optimization algorithm were chosen.

Z-score normalization is applied to the complete data frame of a node's features. This type of normalization was chosen because the feature distribution is relatively uniform and does not contain any strong extremes.

In each case, the first route of a file is read in as a route of class 0, the last route of a file is the optimal route without detours and corresponds to class 1. The distances between two nodes are normalized to the range of 0 to 1. Unlike the Z-score normalization, this normalization was chosen so that some upward outliers would have less influence.

"Source" and "Target" are keywords reserved by StellarGraph for the start and end nodes of edges; the ID of the nodes is stored here. The mapping of the features to the respective nodes is done by means of these IDs; the line from the feature data frame is searched for that has the ID of the "Source" or "Target" node as its index. "Weight" is also used as a keyword for the weighting of the individual edges.

Therefore, in the following, we also describe routes using these graph-specific terms instead of talking about starts, destinations, and distances.

4.2 Graph creation

A graph object can be created from the imported data, which can be used for Machine Learning models in StellarGraph. Specifically, an object of the class *StellarDiGraph* is created, i.e. a directed graph, since the route only runs in a certain direction.

In order to be able to carry out the supervised classification, the graphs must be provided with a label that describes their class. In the binary classification of routes, we use the labels 0 and 1 are used for this purpose.

For the journey time prediction, a graph is provided with a label that contains the journey time required for the route in seconds. Those travel times are stored in a CSV file, which contains the file name of the route file as one column and the travel time determined for the optimal route from this file as another column.

The training models applied are graph classification models with Keras. For processing the individual *StellarDiGraph*-instances, these objects have to be converted into a suitable format. For a supervised graph classification, a *Padded-GraphGenerator* is suitable. This is instantiated with the list of StellarDiGraphs. The generator transforms the data into adjacency matrices and arrays for the features that the Keras model can handle.

4.3 Training

Assuming that the data are independent and identically distributed the GCN model is trained with *k-Cross-Validation* and *Early stopping* to avoid overfitting. For each fold, different training and test samples are used for validation. Without early stopping, there would be a danger of overfitting, as the algorithm would adapt too much to the training data, which would lead to a generalization error. The training is stopped at an early stopping value of x if the loss does not decrease over x epochs. The loss was chosen by us as a metric to optimize the model and is therefore observed.

For the binary classification, a data set consisting of 7708 routes was trained. In each case, 3854 data sets belong to class 0 for a route with detours and class 1

for an optimal route. 3610 graphs are trained, the average number of nodes per route is 69.7, the average number of edges is 71.7.

4.4 Implementation of a DGCNN Model

Fig. 3. Model of the Deep Graph Convolutional Neural Network used

To further improve our prediction result and the accuracy of the classification, we extended our model to a Deep Graph Convolutional Neural Network (DGCNN). This model is based on the End-To-End Deep Graph Convolutional Neural Network architecture that is shown in Figure 3. Unlike the first model, four GCN layers are used here, but their adjacency matrix is $D^{-1}A$ normalized. The last GCN layer is one-dimensional, only this layer is used as input for sorting the nodes in *SortPooling*. The GCN layers and the SortPooling layer are followed by one-dimensional Convolution and Pooling layers to extract local patterns for the sorted node sequence. This is followed by a Fully Connected layer with a dropout of 0.5 until the last layer with the *Sigmoid Activation* function is used to perform binary classification. Each layer has a size of 32 nodes and the mean training time for this model was 33ms per step, which results in a total training time of 2.5 minutes on our machine, which is a 4-GPU A-100 system [1].

The model is trained using data sets with fixed batch sizes for training data and test data. Furthermore, the number of training epochs and the value k , describe to which size the graphs should be scaled.

Since the DGCNN has shown a better performance than the GCN, this model is used for travel time prediction. This improvement in performance can be explained by the fact that the additional layers allow a more complex non-linear function to be learned. The basic model is not changed much, because the learning of the weights for the training data is basically the same, the only difference is that instead of a class a continuous value is output as result. Therefore, the activation function must be changed in the last layer so that the values are not scaled between 0 and 1, but continuous values can also be output above this. In our ongoing experiments, we use the *ReLU* function for this purpose. The loss function must be adapted. In our case, the *Mean Absolute Error* was used.

Table 1. Accuracies for GCN for binary graph classification

GCN	Epochs	Folds	Early Stop	Learning Rate	Batch size	Accuracy
Directed	25	10	25	0.005	64	59.4%
Directed	25	10	25	0.005	128	58.8%
Undirected	50	10	25	0.0005	128	58.5%
Undirected	50	10	25	0.005	128	75.4%
Undirected	50	10	25	0.005	256	72.8%
Undirected	75	10	25	0.005	128	73.7%
Undirected	50	10	25	0.005	512	74.5%
Undirected	50	5	25	0.005	512	65.1%

5 Evaluation

Table 1 shows an overview of different parameterizations with regard to the test accuracies of the dataset. It can be observed that the model performs well with undirected StellarGraph objects, but not with directed StellarDiGraph objects (see lines 1 and 2). The reason for this is the symmetric normalization of the adjacency matrix of the GCN, $D^{-\frac{1}{2}}AD^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, which only performs well for the symmetric adjacency matrix of undirected graphs.

Fig. 4. Accuracy and loss curve for graph classification for the chosen GCN Model

The parameterization with the best accuracy is learning over 50 epochs with 10-fold folded data, a learning rate of 0.005, and a batch size of 128. The table shows only a few exemplary parameterizations, further changes to the existing parameters have also provided similar results in the range above 70% accuracy.

It can be observed that the learning rate for GCN has a large influence on the model's performance - with a value of 0.0005 the model is unreliable and the

Table 2. Accuracies for DGCNN for binary graph classification

DGCNN	Epochs	Learning rate	Batch size	Train Test	k	Train Test%	Accuracy
Directed	30	0.001	200	40	35	0.8 0.2	68.4%
Directed	100	0.01	200	40	50	0.8 0.2	50.0%
Directed	100	0.001	400	80	50	0.8 0.2	75.0%
Directed	100	0.001	200	40	67	0.8 0.2	79.6%
Directed	100	0.001	400	80	67	0.8 0.2	80.9%
Directed	50	0.001	400	80	67	0.8 0.2	76.0%
Directed	100	0.005	200	40	50	0.8 0.2	71.8%
Directed	100	0.0001	400	80	67	0.8 0.2	71.3%
Directed	100	0.0005	400	80	67	0.7 0.3	74.7%
Directed	100	0.0005	200	40	67	0.8 0.2	77.2%
Directed	100	0.0005	400	80	67	0.8 0.2	75.48%
Directed	100	0.0005	200	40	67	0.7 0.3	76.3%

loss is high. With a 5-fold convolution of the data set, the model also did not perform as well as with a 10-fold convolution.

For the parameterization of the penultimate line, the curves for the accuracy and the binary entropy loss can be seen in Figure 4. It can be seen that the values sometimes fluctuate strongly over the epochs; one possible reason for this is that the validation set for the convolution contains outliers. Otherwise, the validation accuracy is higher than the training accuracy. This is due to the fact that dropout is active in the training data, which deactivates some neurons in order to learn. In the validation set, on the other hand, learning takes place with all neurons.

Fig. 5. Accuracy and loss curve for graph classification for the chosen DGCNN Model

A listing of differently parameterized training trials is shown in table 2. These runs were performed on the same data set as the GCN in the previous chapter, except that these graphs were created as directed graphs, i.e. StellarDiGraphs. The best performance was measured over 100 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001.

Fig. 6. Distribution of predictions (Green) to actual travel times (Blue) for 19-20, 21-22, and 23-24 stops

In addition to this good performance for directed graphs, the accuracy for the individual parameterizations is also similar for undirected graphs, but large fluctuations can be noticed in the graph for an accuracy that is higher than the number of epochs when undirected graphs are used. The two graphs shown in 5 run with slight fluctuations, but are otherwise similar in their course. From epoch 60 onwards, slight overfitting can be observed, as the test data get a higher loss and a lower accuracy than the training data.

For the best parameterization found so far, the calculated RMSE is 3708.70 seconds. The distribution of actual to predicted travel times can be seen in Figure 6. Blue are the actual times, and green the predicted ones. On the x -axis the input graphs are indexed, on the y -axis the travel times in seconds are shown. The division into 3 different graphs with a classification into different groups was chosen because an increase in the number of stops in a route leads to a corresponding jump in the ETA. The model was initially calculated completely for routes with 19-24 stops. In trials, it was found that a GCN trained only with routes up to 19 stops could also make accurate predictions for routes with more stops and vice versa. Thus, our model is arbitrarily scalable to smaller or larger areas. A large generalization of the model can therefore be assumed.

Here we can find more parameters to train the DGCNN with and choose a better-fitting architecture. For a first proof of concept, however, these results confirm that GL is suitable for route classification surprisingly clearly.

For our specific case, this means that our model can decide very quickly whether additional passengers can be picked up and brought to their destination due to the low travel time.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented our Graph Learning model that allows us to decide whether a route of the VRP is optimal, or contains detours. We also presented a first approach based on which ETA prediction is possible. The binary classification of the algorithm achieved an accuracy of 80.9%. This allows us to terminate our long computing HGS algorithm early if the model we trained thinks it has already reached an optimal result. Thus, instead of the previously used rigid termination criteria such as the maximum number of iterations or a certain number of iterations without improvement, the prediction from the DGCNN can be used. An approximate solution method of soft computing was applied to real data, acting supportively to a numerical method.

Using our graph learning models we achieve a mean inference time of 184ms, which allows us to get a result very quickly and provides the user with decision support without a long wait. In addition, the models are permanently scalable and applicable to similar problems. For example, if the model should be evaluated for a larger area, this can be done at any time. Also, a transfer and application in another rural area with similar characteristics is possible at any time.

It also turned out that our model can be applied to regions with a similar nature of traffic without any changes and still provides good results. Also, an extension of the considered area is possible without making any adjustments.

Especially in the prediction of the ETA based on graph learning, there are still a lot of optimizations possible. Due to the design of our system, it is very easy to increase the dataset with training and test data with minimal effort. The authors are currently trying to obtain further parameters for the nodes and edges between them in the form of live traffic data. In the future, this should be a practical application to provide users with the ETA of their trip. Due to the special version of route planning in the form of the CVRPPD, the user cannot be given the actual journey time here before the journey begins.

Both of these implementations form a basis for further developments in the area of detour detection for routes with dynamic on-demand stops. For example, different quality criteria on the travel time can be used in order to be able to decide reactively in individual cases whether or not there is too much of a detour for a further stop.

Finally, we believe that with this work we have created a system that can support users in their decision-making and provide a reliable termination criterion for rigid algorithms.

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